

The Strengths and Weakness of Pluralism Theory

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Pluralism theory is well-known as a theoretical tradition used to analyse political actions in modern democratic states. This theory is mainly based upon a perspective that citizens are involved in political arenas through different interest groups, and that political power should be dispersed to secure its own legitimate interests and none of these groups will dominate the system (Miller, 1983: 735). This essay will examine both the strengths and weakness of pluralism theory.

The first strength of this theory is that it clearly addresses and acknowledges the reality of diversity between different groups in the political context. Thus, it gives some space for interest groups whether large or small to compete and participate, based on their interests. This is because the government will protect them to ensure that they will get the same opportunities, even potential groups, such as the church, universities and professional associations. As a consequence, the ideal democratisation will be achieved by the distribution of political power. The interest groups all benefit (Miller, 1983: 737).

The second strength of pluralism theory is that it encourages small groups to develop their tactics and strategies by maintaining their interest. The government is an umpire that guarantees the political system will work and running well. The government will try to solve problems and to mediate all conflicts between interest groups or between interest groups and the government. They, who lose, become opposing groups that will monitor and provide alternative opinions. Therefore, it leads to preventing a tyranny or sovereignty owing to the check and balance system (Self, 1985: 79; Miller, 1983: 735).

However, pluralism theory also has its critics. The main criticism for this theory is that it seems to ignore the reality that there are groups which are dominant over others. These groups can influence the small groups and it could lead to phenomena when small

interest groups only follow them to play chorus songs. The government does not play its role as a referee since the dominant group is too strong and could pressure the government, while small interest groups have less contribution and political pressure (Ellis, 1980: 398).

The other weakness of pluralism theory is its difficulties in implementation. This is because the concept of political power dispersing, needs good coordination. So when coordination cannot be reached, this may lead to inefficiency and may not be effective. For example, when the federal government has lack of coordination with the state governments and is selfishly motivated, the programs probably will not match with the national programs (Self, 1985: 83). Political bias also contributes to the inefficiency of programs. It can be shown by those, who rule some departments and often face a difficulty in distinguishing between the national interest and their own interest groups. This system also makes the process of deciding program priority and policies more complex and too long.

In conclusion, pluralism theory is helpful in identifying political actions which stress the dynamics of interest groups for the ideal political system in democratic countries. However, this system is difficult to implement.

Bibliography:

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